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Effectiveness of Cervical and Lumbosacral Epidural Steroid Injections (ESI) in Motor Vehicle Accident (MVA) Patients

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Abstract

Few studies directly compare Epidural Steroid Injection (ESI) versus Conservative Physical Therapy (CT). This retrospective study aims to compare the efficacy of ESI and CT in motor vehicle accident patients, measured by the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS). The 61 ESI+CT and 109 CT-alone procedures were selected and categorized by cervical or lumbosacral injection region. As hypothesized, VAS reduced significantly for both CT-alone group and ESI+CT group ($p < 0.0001$). On average, as measured by Cohen's d , the VAS reduction was over two standard deviations in ESI+CT group but only over one standard deviation in CT-alone. Therefore, while CT is significantly effective in reducing pain, adding ESI may have increased the effect size. The mean change for Lumbosacral ESI+CT (4.242) is higher than that for Lumbosacral CT-alone (3.490) with a marginal p -value of 0.080 but not significantly different for Cervical ESI+CT (3.800) versus Cervical CT-alone (3.479).

Keywords: Epidural Steroid Injection, Pain Management, Physical Therapy

Introduction

Epidural Steroid Injection (ESI) is a therapeutic modality administered to alleviate radicular pain by delivering a mixture of local anesthetics and corticosteroids to the epidural space in the spine. A previous systematic review (Bicket, et al., 2013) indicated that there are few studies directly comparing ESI versus Conservative Physical Therapy (CT) in motor vehicle accident patients. The goal of this study is to demonstrate that supplementing ESI to CT improves treatment outcomes compared to CT alone for motor vehicle accident patients experiencing cervical and/or lumbosacral radicular pain.

Interlaminar ESI Overview

The corticosteroids reduce inflammation of the nerves by inhibiting activity of the enzyme phospholipase A2 (Bicket, et al., 2013, Huston, 2009, Rados, et al., 2011). There are two main approaches to administering ESI to patients: interlaminar and transforaminal. A previous study indicates that there is no statistically significant difference between the two approaches (Huston, 2009, Rados, et al. 2011). In this study, the interlaminar approach was adopted to applicable patients.

Interlaminar ESI is detailed as followed (Huston, 2009, Qian, 2017, Rados, et al., 2011): the patient is placed in the prone position on the fluoroscopy table and the area of injection is sterilized and prepped with local anesthetic. With the aid of a fluoroscope (a special X-ray), the physician directs an 18-gauge spinal needle through the skin and soft tissue into the epidural space. Fluoroscopy allows the physician to watch the needle in real-time on the fluoroscope monitor. The spinal needle is placed between the lamina of two vertebrae directly from the middle line of the back. This method accesses the epidural space overlying the spinal cord. Needle position is confirmed with injection of radiographic contrast. Then, local anesthetic and steroid medication are delivered into the epidural space. The needle is removed after delivering medications. Ice will be applied to the

area after the procedure, while the patient is being monitored in the recovery room for about 15 to 20 minutes. Most patients can walk around immediately after the procedure. Patients are instructed to continue appropriate exercise and contacted for follow up appointments.

In comparison, conservative therapy (CT) methods include combinations of the following: Physical therapy, Chiropractic therapy, home exercise, and oral NSAIDs.

Research Design and Methodology

The Multispecialty Chiropractic and Medical Clinics (clinics) are Joint Commission accredited facilities in the state of Florida. All motor vehicle accidents patients in the clinics received CT treatment. The cases were selected for this study from the clinic’s electronic medical records. Due to recent ESI implementation in the clinic, there are a limited number of patients who have received both ESI and CT (from March 2017 to September 2017).

Thus, for the ESI+CT group, only 61 patients were evaluated in this study. Data collection is still ongoing to reach the goal of one hundred patients who received the ESI+CT. For the CT-alone group, 109 patients were randomly selected for evaluation.

Upon review of medical records for all selected patients, the age, gender, accident date, initial and final visiting dates, initial and final VAS for the cervical and/or lumbosacral regions, MRI results, chief complaints, physical examination, and ESI injection area and dates were recorded (if applicable). The MRI results indicated disc herniation, bulging, and other findings that may contribute to the pain experienced by the patient. The physical examinations all indicated well-developed and well-nourished patients to eliminate the effect of a lurking variable.

Of the 61 ESI+CT patients (i.e., 27 males and 34 females with average age 45.9 years old), 28 patients received ESI at cervical region only, 31 patients at lumbosacral region only, and 2 at both regions. Among the 33 total lumbosacral ESI+CT procedures, 2 of them were removed from the final data analysis due to inconsistency of VAS recording. Therefore, for the final analysis, the ESI+CT sample size was 30 cervical and 31 lumbosacral procedures.

Of the 109 CT-alone patients (i.e., 51 males and 58 females patients with average age 40.2 years old), the sample size was 97 cervical and 101 lumbosacral procedures because the majority of patients received CT at both regions.

Analysis and Results

It was hypothesized that on average VAS decreases significantly after either treatment, and the effect size of ESI+CT group is larger than that of CT-alone group.

Table 1. VAS in CT-Alone Group

	Cervical (N = 97)		Lumbosacral (N = 101)	
	Initial	Final	Initial	Final
Mean	7.072	3.593	7.248	3.757
SD	1.652	2.588	1.705	2.61

The average initial and final VAS for cervical CT-alone as shown in Table 1 is 7.072 and 3.593, respectively. Using paired t-test, the two-tailed P value is less than 0.0001. By conventional criteria, this difference is considered statistically significant with a mean improvement of 3.479.

The average initial and final VAS for lumbosacral CT-alone as shown in Table 1 is 7.248 and 3.757, respectively. The two-tailed P value is less than 0.0001. By conventional criteria, this difference is considered statistically significant with a mean improvement of 3.491.

Table 2. VAS Pain Scale ESI+CT Treatment

	Cervical (N = 30)		Lumbosacral (N = 31)	
	Initial	Final	Initial	Final
Mean	7.217	3.417	7.726	3.484
SD	1.680	2.118	1.910	2.417

The average initial and final VAS for cervical ESI+CT as shown in Table 2 is 7.217 and 3.417, respectively. The two-tailed P value is less than 0.0001. By conventional criteria, this difference is considered statistically significant with a mean improvement of 3.800.

The average initial and final VAS for lumbosacral ESI+CT as shown in Table 2 is 7.726 and 3.484. The two-tailed P value is less than 0.0001. By conventional criteria, this difference is considered statistically significant with a mean improvement of 4.242.

Mean changes show significant improvement in both groups, with or without ESI supplemented at either cervical or lumbosacral region. Thus, the effectiveness of adding ESI to CT is ambiguous. Therefore, the effect size of mean change needs to be evaluated by controlling the standard deviation. This is because individual variations may differ between the CT-alone and the ESI+CT groups.

Equation 1. Effect Size

$$d = 2 * t\text{-value} / \text{SQRT}(\text{sample size} * 2 - 2) \tag{1}$$

Using the reduced formula above for effect size (Equation 1) recommended by Rosenthal and Rosnow (2008), Cohen’s d is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Meta-Analysis on Effect Size of Mean Change

	Mean Change Between Initial and Final VAS	Effect Size (Cohen’s d) of the Mean Change
Cervical CT	3.479	1.776
Lumbosacral CT	3.491	1.889
Cervical ESI+CT	3.800	2.171
Lumbosacral ESI+CT	4.242	2.389

Overall, as shown in Table 3, as measured Cohen’s d, VAS reduction in CT-alone group was over one standard deviation on average (i.e., Cervical = 1.776 and Lumbosacral = 1.889). By contrast, VAS reduction in ESI+CT group was over two standard deviations on average (i.e., Cervical = 2.171 and Lumbosacral = 2.389). Using unpaired t-test, the mean change for Lumbosacral ESI+CT group (4.242) is higher than the one for Lumbosacral CT-alone group (3.491) with a marginal p-value of 0.080. Yet, the mean change for Cervical ESI+CT group (3.800) is not significantly different from that of Cervical CT-alone group (3.479).

Conclusion

Medical records were reviewed retrospectively in the patients who sustained injuries from motor vehicle accidents and treated in the clinics. Current available data for patients who underwent CT and ESI concludes that, although CT is very effective in pain management, adding ESI increased the effect size, especially for lumbosacral region pain. These results followed the expectations of this study. Nevertheless, due to limited number of ESI+CT procedures and the lack of meta analyses in the literature for this topic, statistic power of this study may not be large enough to reach significance cutoffs. In the future, similar studies with larger sample sizes are needed.

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